

Derivation and application of three-dimensional logical transformation

Mingke Yuan (Paul Yuan), <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5497-0059>

Email: pauyuan@true-physics.com; pauyuan36@gmail.com

Oct 08, 2019

ABSTRACT

The misconception of time and space causes various interpretations and outcomes. In order to restore the true physical meaning of time, this paper emphasizes the definitions of mathematical time and physical time. In this paper, we derived the three-dimensional logical transformation according to the principle of invariance of light speed and three-dimensional setup of two reference frames. The logical transformation is for replacing Lorentz transformation and Galilean transformation.

The Lorentz speed transformation given by Einstein is correct. From the speed transformation, Einstein derived the famous mass-speed equation and mass-energy equation. However, the Lorentz factor is superfluous, and it was eliminated when deriving the Lorentz speed transformation. Without Lorentz factor, the Lorentz transformation becomes one-dimensional logical transformation. That is why the one-dimensional logical speed transformation is exactly the same as the Lorentz speed transformation. Since Lorentz transformation is based on one-dimensional setup of two reference frames, the Lorentz transformation is not applicable for particles moves in three-dimensional space. That is why the three-dimensional Lorentz transformations of physical quantities are contradictory and problematic.

According to the logical transformation and the principle of invariance of relative velocity, we also derived a series of three-dimensional physical formulas and physical quantity transformations. We believe these equations will be useful for high-energy physics, quantum mechanics, and clock correction of GPS. These equations may be also useful for astrophysics.

KEYWORD

Logical transformation; Special relativity; relativistic mechanics; Lorentz transformation; Lorentz factor; covariance; Galilean; space time; High-energy physics; quantum; fundamental physics theory; Maxwell.

Please read Einstein's paper "On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies" [3] to understand the derivation of Lorentz transformation. Please don't label this paper as non-relativistic until you read it carefully by logical thinking. This paper is a continuation of papers [1] and [2]. In paper [2], we have proved that Einstein's postulate of invariance of light speed is correct, and have derived the principle of invariance of relative velocity. In this paper, we apply these two principles to derive the three-dimensional Logical transformation and a series of formulas. We don't need Lorentz factor postulate or relativistic spacetime postulate.

One hundred and twenty-four years ago, Einstein pointed out that mass is not invariant. This conclusion is undoubtedly correct. Einstein also pointed out that a moving "clock" is slower than a stationary "clock". For understanding what the "clock" is here, we must clarify the true physical meaning of this statement.

1. Time and space definitions, and transformation between two reference frames

The mysterious invariance of light speed is a very normal natural phenomenon, but it is impossible to dominate time and space. The two observers on two relative motion reference frames have opposite views regarding which reference frame is stationary. The space (x, y, z) is defined by a frame. If a frame defined by an observer as the stationary reference frame, the space (x, y, z) defined by this reference frame represents physical space. And the space defined by another frame (x', y', z') , which has relative motion to the reference frame, is mathematical space.

The mathematical space and physical space do not coincide. The mathematical space (x', y', z') moves in the physical space, just as particles moves in the physical space. The physical meaning of frame transformation is to transform particle motions from physical space into mathematical space (x', y', z') . The mathematical space (x', y', z') is also defined as physical space by the observer who is in the frame, because frame (x', y', z') is defined as stationary reference frame by the observer. Transformation equations are for communications between observer (x, y, z) and observer (x', y', z') . Only one physical space exists, but observer (x, y, z) and observer (x', y', z') do not have mutual agreement for which frame represents physical space. If you stand on the moon, the sky you see is physical space; if you stand on the earth, the sky you see is also physical space. However, these two "physical spaces" do not coincide due to the motion between moon and earth. That is why light speed is always equal to c in moon frame or earth frame. Spaces are shift each other, not contracted each other.

In this paper, we divide time into natural time, physical time and math time. The natural time is the scope of cosmology research, which is not discussed in this paper. Physical time is defined by physics. Physical time is measured by a standard clock, which is located in London Greenwich. We use symbol t to represent physical time for frame S, and use symbol t' to represent physical time for frame S'. Please note that physical time t' and t are independent variables, which are never changed by any observation. The interval and rate of time t' are always equal to interval and rate of time t . Math time is a dependent variable, which is defined by a function or an equation. We use symbol t'^* to represent math time for frame S', and use symbol t^* to represent math time for frame S. In this paper, we use $t'^* = f(t, x, v)$ or $t^* = f(t', x', v')$ to represent math time. Math time depends on observation. "Moving clock is slower" means $t'^* < t'$.

Fig. 1 is one-dimensional setup for deriving Galilean transformation and Lorentz transformation. Frame S' and frame S are in relative uniform motion, which speed is v . The x' -axis and x -axis overlap each other. Particle Q is moving in x -axis positive direction. Please note that there is no natural relationship of time between frames S' and S unless we study particle Q motion in both frames. If the

speed of particle Q in frame S is u , and we stand on frame S , can we figure out the speed u'^* of particle Q in frame S' ? This operation is called **transformation**. The math speed u'^* from a transformation equation must be equal to u' value, which is measured in frame S' . This is very clear; otherwise the transformation equation is useless.

Since $u'^* = dx'^*/dt'^*$, if we know $t'^* = f(t, x, v)$ and $x'^* = f(t, x, v)$, we will obtain u'^* . The $t'^* = f(t, x, v)$ and $x'^* = f(t, x, v)$ is called basic transformation equations. For clear discussion, we use symbol "*" to represent the math

quantity in Section 1 to 4. If math quantity is equal to physical quantity, the math equation is correct. Now, we have three different transformations: 1) Galilean transformation; 2) Lorentz transformation; 3) Logical transformation (It is derived in this paper). Which transformation is correct?

The paper [1] gives the necessary and sufficient conditions to verify the correctness of transformation equations between two reference frames, that is: "The result of transformation not only satisfies the requirements of the principle of relativity, but also satisfies the measurement values of the physical quantities in frame S' or satisfies the experimental results in frame S' or satisfies logical analysis".

2. The comparison of three transformations from frame S to frame S'

Please note that the following three transformations are only for a particle moving in x -axis positive direction. If a particle moves in three-dimensional space, the following three transformations are invalid. For three dimensional velocity transformations, please see Section 6 in this paper.

The Galilean transformation:

$$x'^* = x - vt \tag{1}$$

$$t'^* = t \tag{2}$$

$$u'^* = u - v \tag{3}$$

The Lorentz transformation [3]:

$$x'^* = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(x - vt) \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \tag{4}$$

$$t'^* = (1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2})(t - vx/c^2) \tag{5}$$

$$u'^* = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \tag{19}$$

$$y'^* = y \quad z'^* = z \tag{6}$$

The one-dimensional Logical transformation (see Section 5):

$$x'^* = x - vt \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \tag{17}$$

$$t'^* = t - vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v, v < c \tag{18}$$

$$u'^* = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \tag{19}$$

The Eq.(1) and Eq.(17) are the same. From Fig 1, we can easily get the geometric relationship between S' and S , so $x' = x - vt$, i.e. $x'^* = x'$, math distance x'^* is equal to physical distance x' . Why equation (4) and (5) include Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$? This looks very mysterious. Someone may say: "It is relativistic spacetime".

The principle of the invariance of light speed can be simply written as:

$$c' = c \quad c \text{ is a constant} \tag{7}$$

Fig. 1

This principle is a necessary condition to verify the correctness of a transformation equation, i.e. if $c'^* = c'$ (where c'^* is the result from a transformation equation, and c' is the light speed measured in reference frame S'), the transformation equation satisfies the necessary condition of correctness; if $c'^* \neq c'$, the transformation equation is incorrect.

Using this criterion, we found that Galilean speed transformation is incorrect. If the particle Q is a photon in Fig.1, from Eq.(3), we get

$$c'^* = c - v \quad \text{i.e. } c'^* \neq c'$$

Someone may say that the Eq.(3) does not work for a photon, but it will work for other particles. Well, please read the paper [1]. If we doesn't postulate $t'^* \neq t$, we cannot get Eq.(3). Thus, we conclude that equation (2) is incorrect. Since $v \ll c$, if frame S' moves at low speed, we are hard to detect the error. For particles traveling at high velocities and energies, the Galilean transformation and the classical Newtonian mechanics does not work. Please note that $u' = u - v$ is only for the case of $v \ll c$ does not mean $x' = x - vt$ is also only for the case of $v \ll c$. We should not deny geometric relationship based on the postulate of time dilation and space contraction. We believe the invariance of light speed is a principle of nature. Please read paper [2].

Please read Einstein's paper [3]. Einstein first derived Eq.(19) from Eq.(4) and (5). If the particle is a photon in Fig.1, from Eq.(19), we get

$$c'^* = (c - v)/(1 - vc/c^2) = c, \quad \text{i.e. } c'^* = c = c'$$

Thus, we conclude that equation (19) satisfies the necessary condition of correctness. Does equation (19) satisfy the sufficient condition of correctness? Einstein derived following important formulas from Eq.(19):

$$m = \gamma m_0 \tag{50}$$

where $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - u^2/c^2} > 1$, m_0 is mass measurement when a particle is at rest. m is mathematical mass when a particle is moving. The Eq.(50) is called the relationship between mass and speed. From Eq.(50), Einstein derived a surprising formula:

$$E = mc^2 \tag{52}$$

E is total mathematical kinetic energy when a particle is moving. The Eq.(52) is called the relationship between mass and energy. Since formula (50) and (52) has been confirmed for a large number of physical experiments, we conclude that equation (19) is correct, and math m^* or E^* is equal to physical m or E .

However, a question is asked here. Does the correctness of Eq.(19) prove that Eq.(4) and (5) are also correct? Another question is: Since Lorentz transformation Eq.(4),(5),(19) is based on Fig. 1, which is only for a particle moving direction parallel to x -axis, if a particle moves at an angle with x -axis or moves in three-dimensional space, does the Lorentz transformation still hold true? Does the time transformation Eq.(5) still hold true along y' -axis or z' -axis directions? There is no relative motion in y' -axis or z -axis between frames S' and S , why $t'^* \neq t'$, $t'^* \neq t$?

3. Time and distance transformations from frame S to frame S'

The speed transformations of Lorentz transformation and Logical transformation are the same, but their time and distance transformations are different. Which one is correct? Let's take a closer look at how the speed transformation is derived from Lorentz transformation. According to the speed definition, the Eq.(19) can be derived from Eqs.(4) and (5):

$$u'^* = \frac{dx'^*}{dt'^*} = \frac{\frac{dx'^*}{dt}}{\frac{dt'^*}{dt}} = \frac{\frac{1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \frac{d}{dt}(x-vt)}{1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \frac{d}{dt}(t-\frac{vx}{c^2})}}{\frac{d}{dt}(x-vt)} = \frac{d}{dt}(x-vt) = (u-v)/(1-vu/c^2)$$

From the above derivation, we are surprised that the Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ was eliminated! After the Lorentz factor is removed from Eqs.(4) and (5), the Lorentz transformation becomes the Logical transformation, i.e. Eqs.(17) and (18). Obviously, the correctness of Eq.(19) does not prove that Eq.(4) and (5) are also correct.

Let's take an example to discuss a particle motion trajectory in space-time of frames S' and S. If we set $u = 0.9c$, $v = 0.5c$, we can get following equations as per above transformation equations:

Per Galilean transformation: $t'^* = t$, $x'^* = x - 0.5ct$

Per Lorentz transformation: $t'^* = (1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(t - 0.5x/c)$, $x'^* = (1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(x - 0.5ct)$

Per Logical transformation: $t'^* = t - 0.5x/c$, $x'^* = x - 0.5ct$

Per Strange transformation: $t'^* = (\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(t - 0.5x/c)$, $x'^* = (\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(x - 0.5ct)$

To illustrate that the correct speed equation does not mean the time and distance equations are also correct, we have arbitrarily created a strange transformation:

$$x'^* = (\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(x - vt)$$

$$t'^* = (\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})(t - vx/c^2)$$

We can choose a few points and get a variable table of t'^* and x'^* as per $t'^* = f(t, x)$, $x'^* = f(t, x)$.

A particle motion trajectory in space-time of frames S	A particle motion trajectory in space-time of frames S'			
	Galilean transformation	Lorentz transformation	Logical transformation	Strange transformation
$t = 0$ $x = 0$	$t'^* = 0$ $x'^* = 0$	$t'^* = 0$ $x'^* = 0$	$t'^* = 0$ $x'^* = 0$	$t'^* = 0$ $x'^* = 0$
$t = 1 \times 10^3$ $x = 9 \times 10^2 c$	$t'^* = 1 \times 10^3$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^2 c$	$t'^* = 1.15(5.5 \times 10^2)$ $x'^* = 1.15(4 \times 10^2 c)$	$t'^* = 5.5 \times 10^2$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^2 c$	$t'^* = 0.87(5.5 \times 10^2)$ $x'^* = 0.87(4 \times 10^2 c)$
$t = 1 \times 10^4$ $x = 9 \times 10^3 c$	$t'^* = 1 \times 10^4$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^3 c$	$t'^* = 1.15(5.5 \times 10^3)$ $x'^* = 1.15(4 \times 10^3 c)$	$t'^* = 5.5 \times 10^3$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^3 c$	$t'^* = 0.87(5.5 \times 10^3)$ $x'^* = 0.87(4 \times 10^3 c)$
$t = 1 \times 10^5$ $x = 9 \times 10^4 c$	$t'^* = 1 \times 10^5$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^4 c$	$t'^* = 1.15(5.5 \times 10^4)$ $x'^* = 1.15(4 \times 10^4 c)$	$t'^* = 5.5 \times 10^4$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^4 c$	$t'^* = 0.87(5.5 \times 10^4)$ $x'^* = 0.87(4 \times 10^4 c)$
$t = 1 \times 10^6$ $x = 9 \times 10^5 c$	$t'^* = 1 \times 10^6$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^5 c$	$t'^* = 1.15(5.5 \times 10^5)$ $x'^* = 1.15(4 \times 10^5 c)$	$t'^* = 5.5 \times 10^4$ $x'^* = 4 \times 10^4 c$	$t'^* = 0.87(5.5 \times 10^5)$ $x'^* = 0.87(4 \times 10^5 c)$

We can draw a space-time graph of the particle motion trajectory as shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 2 shows all lines are straight lines, i.e. they are linear equations if v is a constant. Particle speed is the sloping rate of a straight line:

Speed of a particle = $\tan \beta = x'^*/t'^*$

The line OQ represents the particle motion trajectory in the spacetime of frame S. The line OA' represents the particle motion trajectory in frame S' as per Galilean transformation. The lines OD' , OC' and OB' respectively represents the particle motion trajectory in frame S' as per "strange" transformation,

Q - The apticle in frame S space-time.
A' - The apticle in frame S' space-time per Galilean tran.
B' - The apticle in frame S' space-time per Lorentz tran.
C' - The apticle in frame S' space-time per Logical tran.

Fig. 2

Logical transformation and Lorentz transformation. The lines OD' , OC' and OB' overlap since their speed transformations are all the same. It means we can obtain the same u' by many groups of x' and t' .

From Fig. 2, we can see that Galilean transformation shows no time change, i.e. $t - t'^* = 0$. As per Logical transformation, the time change $t - t'^* = vx/c^2$ is not a constant, it is proportional to the physical distance x ; the distance change $x - x'^* = vt$ is also not a constant, it is proportional to the physical time t .

Referring to Fig. 2, the value of time change as per Logical transformation is larger than the value of time change as per Lorentz transformation. Therefore, we need to properly adjust satellite time (satellite "clock") to accurately calculate satellite functionality.

Fig. 2 does not mean that we have two physical space-times. The reference frame S represents physical space-time while t'^* and x'^* represent mathematical space-time. Time and distance transformations represent the relationship between the mathematical space-time and the physical space-time for DERIVING a speed transformation. If the time and distance transformations are correct, we can predict a particle motion trajectory in frame S' correctly.

4. Three-dimensional Lorentz transformations from frame S to frame S'

As we discussed in Section 2, the following Lorentz speed transformation is correct.

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (19)$$

As shown in Fig. 3, if a particle motion direction is at an angle to x -axis, three-dimensional velocity of Lorentz transformation is given [4]:

$$u'^*_x = (u_x - v)/(1 - vu_x/c^2) \quad (8)$$

$$u'^*_y = u_y/[\gamma_v (1 - vu_x/c^2)] \quad (9)$$

$$u'^*_z = u_z/[\gamma_v (1 - vu_x/c^2)] \quad (10)$$

Where $\gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ is called Lorentz factor.

Eq.(9) and (10) are very strange. There is no relative motion between y' -axis and y -axis or z' -axis and z -axis, why u'^*_y and u'^*_z are affected by v ? Why is not $u'_y = u_y$ and $u'_z = u_z$. If the Eq.(8), (9),(10) are correct, they should satisfy following equation:

$$u'^2 = u'^2_x + u'^2_y + u'^2_z \quad (11)$$

Obviously, substituting Eq. (8), (9), (10), (19) into above equation, the Eq. (11) does not hold good. According to the criterion for verifying the correctness of a transformation equation between two reference frames, satisfying the principle of relativity is the necessary conditions [1]. Referring to Fig.2, if we draw a graph as per Eqs.(8),(9),(10) in three-dimensional space-time, the particle motion trajectory will be a curve line. As per the requirements of the principle of relativity, if a particle motion trajectory is a straight line in reference frame S , then the particle motion trajectory in frame S' should also be a straight line since v is a constant along x -axis. Therefore, the Eq.(8),(9) and (10) are not compatible with the principle of relativity. Does the Lorentz factor represent bending spacetime?

There are a lot of unable-to-explain problem for three-dimensional Lorentz transformation, such as acceleration transformation, energy transformation, force transformation.

The three-dimensional momentum of Lorentz transformation is given [4]:

$$p'^*_x = p_x \gamma_v (u_x - v) / u_x \quad \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad (12)$$

$$p'^*_y = p_y \quad (13)$$

$$p'^*_z = p_z \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3

Again, Eq.(13) and (14) are very strange. Since the velocities are not the same in y -axis and z -axis directions between frames S' and S as per Eqs. (9) and (10), why Eqs. (13) and (14) indicate their momentums are the same in directions of y -axis and z -axis between frames S' and S ? We all know $p = m u$. Therefore, no one can explain Eqs. (13) and (14). If the Eq.(12),(13),(14) are correct, they should satisfy following equation:

$$p'^2 = p_x'^2 + p_y'^2 + p_z'^2 \quad (15)$$

Let's see one more sample. Following is three-dimensional magnetic field and electric field of Lorentz transformation [3] [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} E'_x &= E_x & B'_x &= B_x \\ E'_y &= \gamma_v(E_y - vB_z) & B'_y &= \gamma_v(B_y + v/c^2 E_z) \\ E'_z &= \gamma_v(E_z + vB_y) & B'_z &= \gamma_v(B_z - v/c^2 E_y) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$$

Light is an electromagnetic wave, which is independent of v , i.e. $c'^*=c'=c$. The electromagnetic phenomenon is related to the relative motion of electromagnetic, and E and B are not a function of v (v is the relative speed between the ground and a train). If we do an experiment on a moving train (In this case, the train is a stationary frame), according to the principle of relativity, the electromagnetic phenomenon will be the same as we do that experiment on the ground. However, the above Eq.(16) states that magnetic field and electric field depend on the moving speed of the train, i.e. $E'^* = f(v)$, $B'^* = f(v)$. Thus, the electromagnetic phenomenon will be changed in different reference frames. This does not conform to the principle of relativity, which is a necessary condition to verify the correctness of a transformation equation. Comparing Eq.(16) and Eq.(8), (9), (10), the transformations of x -axis direction are normal (no Lorentz factor γ_v), but the transformations of y -axis and z -axis directions are related to Lorentz factor γ_v . Why? The reason is that Lorentz transformation is based on one-dimensional setup (Fig. 1), so it is not suitable for particles moving three-dimensional.

If the Eq.(16) is correct, it should satisfies following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} E'^2 &= E_x'^2 + E_y'^2 + E_z'^2 \\ B'^2 &= B_x'^2 + B_y'^2 + B_z'^2 \end{aligned}$$

As we discussed in Section 2, 3 and 4, the problems of Lorentz transformation and Galilean transformation are obvious. It is necessary to derive a new transformation to replace Lorentz transformations and Galilean transformation. This new transformation is called Logical transformation. We will obtain a lot of equations and formulas by applying the three-dimensional Logical transformation. The forms of some equations are the same as relativistic mechanics.

5. The derivation of one-dimensional Logical transformation

Please read the paper [2] to understand why $c' = c$. Referring to Fig. 4, if there is a relative motion between frame S' and S , a natural space point, at which a photon was emitted, cannot be a stationary point in both frame S' and S mutually. If observer S views that point in frame S , it is a stationary point while that point located at frame S' is moving; if observer S' views that point in frame S' , it is a stationary point while that point located at frame S is moving. The motion state of that point depends on a reference frame since there is not an absolute stationary frame in the universe.

Please note that observer S and observer S' use the same clocks defined by physics to measure time and the same rulers defined by physics to measure distance. Therefore, the distance between two points in physical space is the same regardless of reference frames. Physical clocks are the same regardless of reference frames S' or S.

Photone Q motion in frame S' is viewed by observer S

Fig. 4

Referring Fig. 4, the relative distance between the origins of frames S' and S is the same in both frames S' and S. Thus, $v't' = vt$, and the moving direction is opposite, $v' = -v$. If the particle Q in Fig. 4 is a photon, we can mathematically figure out the time relationship between frames S' and S. When the moving y'-axis overlaps with the stationary y-axis, let a light ray be emitted at the origin of frame S. Now, we focus a photon, which is moving along positive direction of x-axis.

Observer S stands on reference frame S to view the photon motion which is in frame S'. The photon first reaches the origin of frame S', and then reaches point B in frame S'. The math distance is $x_0'^* + x'^*$. The math time it spent is $t_0'^* + t'^*$. Referring to Fig. 4, we get $t = t_0'^* + t'^*$ and $x = x_0'^* + x'^*$. The t and x are physical time and physical distance when observer S views the photon motion which is in frame S.

When observer S' views the photon motion in frame S', the physical time is t', and the distance is x', which is the photon moves from the origin of frame S' to point B. From Fig. 4, we get $x'^* = x'$, and $x = x_0'^* + x' = vt + x'$. Thus, we conclude that math distance is equal to physical distance, i.e. $x'^* = x'$. Also from Fig. 4, we can see that math time is not equal to physical time, i.e. $t'^* \neq t'$ since t' and t were reset at the moment when y'-axis overlaps with y-axis, i.e. $t' = t$. (t'^* is from S viewing S').

$x = vt + x'$ is the distance relationship between frame S' and S. What is the time relationship between frame S' and S? Viewing the photon motion in frame S, the photon moving speed in frame S' is c', moving distance from origin S to origin S' is vt, so $t_0'^* = vt/c'$. On the other hand, in frame S, the photon spent time t to reach point B, i.e. $t = x/c$. Due to $c' = c$, we get $t_0'^* = vx/c^2$. Thus, when viewing in frame S, the time relationship between frame S' and S is:

$$t = vx/c^2 + t'^*$$

Where t'^* is math time, which is observer S in frame S views the photon motion which is frame S'.

Therefore, we obtain the distance relationship $x'^* = f(x, t, v)$ and the time relationship $t'^* = f(x, t, v)$ between frames S' and S. These relationships are called logical transformation. Due to $x'^* = x'$, we use symbol x' instead of x'^*.

One-dimensional Logical transformation:

$$x' = x - vt \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \tag{17}$$

$$t'^* = t - vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v, \quad v < c \tag{18}$$

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \tag{19}$$

The Eq.(19) is derived from Eq.(17) and (18):

$$u' = \frac{dx'}{dt'^*} = \frac{dx'/dt}{dt'^*/dt} = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2)$$

In Section 2, we have verified that equation (19) is correct, so we use symbol u' instead of u'^*. For the time value in frame S', since the view of observer S differs the view of observer S', we must use **math t'^* instead of physical t'** to obtain the **correct speed of a particle** in frame S'. The physical time t'

in frame S' is equal to physical time t in frame S . In fact, there is no math time t'^* if we don't study a particle motion in both frames S and S' .

The Eq.(18) is derived according to $c' = c$. If $c' = c$ is correct, the Eq.(18) should be correct. Therefore, the Eq.(17), (18), (19) are applicable to all particle motions. However, if a particle moves along y -axis or z -axis direction, the Eq.(18) will be invalid. In this case, since there is no relative motion in y -axis or z -axis direction between frames S' and S , it will be $t'^* = t' = t$ (clocks of t' and t was reset at same time) and $u' = u$. Hence, according to the setup of two frames shown on Fig. 1, we obtain

The complete form of one-dimensional Logical transformation:

$$x' = x - vt \quad x'-\text{axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \quad (17)$$

$$t'^* = t - vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v, v < c \quad (18)$$

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (19)$$

$$y' = y \quad z' = z \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (20)$$

$$t'^* = t \quad \text{when particle moving along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (21)$$

$$u' = u \quad u \text{ direction is along } y\text{-axis or } z\text{-axis} \quad (22)$$

6. The derivation of three-dimensional Logical transformation

The one-dimensional Logical transformation is only for a particle moves in x -axis direction. If a particle moves at an angle to x -axis, and if two particles move in different orientations in 3D space, the Eq.(17),(18),(19) cannot help. In order to accurately locate GPS, we need to change the satellite's "clock". For studying particles traveling at high velocities and energies, we need to use particle frame's math "clock". Since satellite motion, particle frame motion are not parallel to Earth's coordinate system, we need three-dimensional Logical transformation. For deriving three-dimensional Logical transformation, we use velocity to replace speed, and use vector to replace scalar. For convenient, we use **text bold** symbols to represent vectors.

Referring to Fig. 5, the origin of frame S' is at B , and the origin of frame S is at A . B and A are in relative uniform motion (v) in any ordination, and a particle C is moving along the line AB . If we know the physical quantity of particle C in frame S , can we figure out the physical quantity of particle C in frame S' ?

The motions of B and C are in 3 D space. The direction of v and u are in line.

Fig. 5

Let a light ray be emitted at point A when point A and B overlap. At this moment, we reset clocks of t' and t , i.e. $t' = t = 0$,

$x' = y' = z' = 0, x = y = z = 0$. Viewing in frame S , a photon moves along line AB from A to C in frame S , and the displacement is r_{AC} , physical time is t , velocity is c . Viewing in frame S' , the photon in frame S' first moves along line AB to B . The displacement is r'_{AB} ; math time is t'^* ; velocity is c' . And then, the photon in frame S' moves along line BC to C . The displacement is r'_{BC} ; math time is t'^* . We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{r}_{AC} &= \boldsymbol{r}'_{AB} + \boldsymbol{r}'_{BC} = \boldsymbol{v}t + \boldsymbol{r}'_{BC} & (23) \\ t &= t'^* + t'^* = \boldsymbol{v}t/c' + t'^* \end{aligned}$$

Since $t = \boldsymbol{r}_{AC} / c$ and $c' = c$, we obtain:

$$t = \boldsymbol{v}\boldsymbol{r}_{AC} / c^2 + t'^* \quad (24)$$

From Eq.(23) and Eq.(24), we obtain the three-dimensional Logical transformation of displacement and time:

$$\boldsymbol{r}'_{BC} = \boldsymbol{r}_{AC} - \boldsymbol{v}t \quad (25)$$

$$t'^* = t - \boldsymbol{v}\boldsymbol{r}_{AC} / c^2 \quad (26)$$

From Eq.(25) and Eq.(26), and noticing $d\mathbf{v}/dt = 0$, we can derive the velocity Logical transformation.

$$\mathbf{u}' = d\mathbf{y}'_{BC}/dt'^* = (d\mathbf{y}'_{BC}/dt)/(dt'^*/dt) = (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v})/(1 - \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}/c^2)$$

Three-dimensional Logical transformation:

$$\mathbf{y}'_{BC} = \mathbf{y}_{AC} - \mathbf{v}t \quad (25)$$

$$t'^* = t - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{y}_{AC}/c^2 \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{u}' = (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v})/(1 - \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}/c^2) \quad (27)$$

Where \mathbf{y}_{AC} is a particle location vector in frame S; \mathbf{y}'_{BC} is the particle location vector in frame S'; t is physical time in frame S; t'^* is math time when frame S' is viewed in frame S; \mathbf{v} is uniform relative velocity between frames S' and S, and \mathbf{v} is a constant vector; \mathbf{u} is the particle velocity in frame S; \mathbf{u}' is the particle velocity in frame S'.

$$|\mathbf{y}_{AC}| = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad |\mathbf{y}'_{BC}| = \sqrt{x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2}$$

$$\mathbf{v} = v_x\mathbf{i} + v_y\mathbf{j} + v_z\mathbf{k} \quad \mathbf{u} = u_x\mathbf{i} + u_y\mathbf{j} + u_z\mathbf{k} \quad \mathbf{u}' = u'_x\mathbf{i} + u'_y\mathbf{j} + u'_z\mathbf{k}$$

If the x' -axis of frame S' and the x -axis of frame S overlap, and if the particle moves along x -axis positive direction, the three-dimensional Logical transformation becomes Eqs.(17),(18),(19).

One-dimensional Logical transformation:

$$x' = x - vt \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (17)$$

$$t'^* = t - vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v, \quad v < c \quad (18)$$

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is the same as } v \quad (19)$$

Please note that equation $u'_x = (u_x - v)/(1 - vu_x/c^2)$ is incorrect, since the directions of \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{u} should be the same or opposite. u_x is the component of \mathbf{u} along the x -axis, and the directions of \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{u} are different.

Similarly, if we stand on frame S' and observe a particle motion which is in frame S, we can obtain

Three-dimensional Logical inverse transformation:

$$\mathbf{y}_{AC} = \mathbf{y}'_{BC} + \mathbf{v}t' \quad (28)$$

$$t^* = t' + \mathbf{v}\mathbf{y}'_{BC}/c^2 \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = (\mathbf{u}' + \mathbf{v})/(1 + \mathbf{u}'\mathbf{v}/c^2) \quad (30)$$

One-dimensional Logical inverse transformation:

$$x = x' + vt' \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \quad (31)$$

$$t^* = t' + vx'/c^2 \quad u' \text{ direction is the same as } x'\text{-axis, } v \text{ direction is opposite to } u' \quad (32)$$

$$u = (u' + v)/(1 + vu'/c^2) \quad u' \text{ direction is the same as } x'\text{-axis} \quad (33)$$

Due to $\mathbf{v}' = -\mathbf{v}$, the Logical inverse transformation is equivalent to a particle moving in opposite direction of \mathbf{v} . When a particle moves in opposite direction of \mathbf{v} , the transformation is as follows.

Three-dimensional Logical transformation when \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{u} directions are opposite:

$$\mathbf{y}'_{BC} = \mathbf{y}_{AC} + \mathbf{v}t \quad (34)$$

$$t'^* = t + \mathbf{v}\mathbf{y}_{AC}/c^2 \quad (35)$$

$$\mathbf{u}' = (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v})/(1 + \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}/c^2) \quad (36)$$

One-dimensional Logical transformation when u and v directions are opposite:

$$x' = x + vt \quad x'\text{-axis and } x\text{-axis overlap each other} \quad (37)$$

$$t'^* = t + vx/c^2 \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is opposite to } v, \quad v < c \quad (38)$$

$$u' = (u + v)/(1 + vu/c^2) \quad \text{when } u \text{ direction is opposite to } v \quad (39)$$

7. The physical meaning of time transformation, and the notion of time and space

When we stand in reference frame S to figure out the physical quantity relationship between frames S' and S, we must use mathematical time t'^* of frame S' instead of physical time t' . The physical time t' in frame S' is equal to the physical time t in frame S, i.e. S' clock and S clock are the same. They are atomic clocks which represent the standard clocks at London Greenwich. The mathematical time t'^* is slower if the moving direction a particle is the same as the moving direction of frame S'. The mathematical time t'^* is faster if the moving direction of a particle is opposite to the moving direction of frame S'. The time difference, which is $\Delta t = t - t'^* = v\gamma_{AC}/c^2$, is equal to the time of a light ray propagating from S-origin to S'-origin. Unless we study particle motions, there is no mathematical time and there is no time transformation between frames S' and S.

In our daily life, we have to correct our watch to suit time zoon when we are traveling. If we are on an airplane from London to New York, our watch need to be changed continuously. The distance between two points in physical space is invariant regardless of reference systems, because physical distance is defined by physics and mathematics.

All motions are relative. There is no an absolute stationary frame in natural space. Natural space is not an absolute stationary frame. An absolute stationary reference frame only exits in human brain. However, we can define a frame as "absolute" stationary frame, such as the Sun. We can define physical time and physical distance as natural time and natural space.

If frames S' and S are in relative motion, a space point, at which a light ray is emitted, is a stationary point when you view it in frames S while that point in frame S' is moving. If you view it in frame S', the space point is also a stationary point while that point in frame S is moving. A space point in frame S and the same space point in frame S' do not coincide due to the relative motion between frames S' and S'. This is why $c' = c$.

8. The invariant relative velocity between two particles

Referring to Fig. 6, we use symbol u_{CB} to represent relative velocity between particle C and particle B. The direction of relative velocity is along the line CB. Relative velocity u_{CB} is the velocity of particle C in frame S' which its origin is at point B. If the directions of particle C and B are opposite, as per Eq.(36), the relative velocity between particles C and B is:

$$u_{CB} = (u_C + u_B)/(1 + u_C u_B/c^2) \tag{40}$$

Where the directions of u_C and u_B are opposite.

If the directions of particles C and B are the same, as per Eq.(27), the relative velocity between particles C and B is:

$$u_{CB} = (u_C - u_B)/(1 - u_C u_B/c^2) \tag{41}$$

Where the directions of u_C and u_B are the same.

The principle of relativity is based on the principle of invariance of relative velocity. In paper [2], we have proved that relative velocity is invariant regardless of reference frames. But paper [2] uses one-dimensional simple setup of two frames, which the direction of u_C and u_B are along x-axis. If two particles are moving in three-dimensional space as shown in Fig.6, is the relative velocity u_{CB} invariant?

As shown in Fig. 6, the relative velocity between particles C and B in frame S is:

$$u_{CB} = (u_C + u_B)/(1 + u_C u_B/c^2) \quad u_B \text{ is a constant velocity} \tag{40}$$

As shown in Fig. 7, viewing in frame S, and as per Eq.(27), (36), the velocities of particles B and C in frame S' are:

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

$$\mathbf{u}'_B = (\mathbf{u}_B - \mathbf{v}) / (1 - \mathbf{u}_B \mathbf{v} / c^2) \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbf{u}'_C = (\mathbf{u}_C + \mathbf{v}) / (1 + \mathbf{u}_C \mathbf{v} / c^2) \quad (43)$$

If we view the motions of particles B and C in frame S' , as per Eq.(40), the relative velocity between particles C and B in frame S' is (B is the origin of a frame):

$$\mathbf{u}'_{CB} = (\mathbf{u}'_C + \mathbf{u}'_B) / (1 + \mathbf{u}'_C \mathbf{u}'_B / c^2) \quad (44)$$

Substituting Eq. (42), (43) into Eq. (44), we obtain:

$$\mathbf{u}'_{CB} = (\mathbf{u}_C + \mathbf{u}_B) / (1 + \mathbf{u}_C \mathbf{u}_B / c^2) = \mathbf{u}_{CB}$$

Due to $\mathbf{u}'_{CB} = \mathbf{u}_{CB}$, the relative velocity \mathbf{u}_{CB} is invariant regardless of reference frame S or S' .

9. The applications of three-dimensional Logical transformation

According to the three-dimensional Logical transformation, Eqs.(25),(26),(27), we can derive the mass-velocity equation by applying the principle of invariance of relative velocity. From the mass-velocity equation, we can derive the mass-energy equation and kinetic energy equation. From the three-dimensional Logical transformation and mass-velocity equation, we can derive the correct formula of Newton's second law, and the physical quantity transformations from reference frame S to frame S' , such as, the transformations of momentum, mass, energy, acceleration, force.

9.1 The derivation of the relationship of mass and velocity

Classical mechanics postulates that mass is invariant. But Newton's second law can be written as $F = dp/dt = d(mv)/dt$, i.e. $d(mv) = Fdt$ or $\Delta(mv) = F\Delta t$. We can see that mass m is associated with speed of the object, magnitude of the force and duration of the force. Since $v = at = Ft/m$, if m is invariant, as long as the force F is large enough or the duration of the force is long enough, the speed v will tend to infinity, $v \rightarrow \infty > c$. Obviously, it violates the postulate of light speed is the maximum speed [2].

Referring to Fig. 8, let the masses of particle A and B are equal when they are at rest in frame S , i.e. $m_A = m_B$. If particles A and B are in relative motion, we set the origin of the frame S at point C , which is a middle point between AB , i.e. $AC = BC$. In frame S , \mathbf{u}_B and \mathbf{u}_A are equal but the directions are opposite. As per Eq.(40), we obtain the relative velocity between particles B and A :

$$\mathbf{u}_{BA} = (\mathbf{u}_B + \mathbf{u}_A) / (1 + \mathbf{u}_B \mathbf{u}_A / c^2) = 2\mathbf{u}_B / (1 + \mathbf{u}_B^2 / c^2) \quad (45)$$

According to the principle of invariance of relative velocity, if we move the origin of frame S , the relative velocity \mathbf{u}_{BA} is no change. As shown on Fig. 9, we reset the origin of frame S at point A . Since point A is stationary, the velocity \mathbf{v} of particle B in new frame S is the relative velocity between particles B and A . Thus,

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u}_{BA} = 2\mathbf{u}_B / (1 + \mathbf{u}_B^2 / c^2) \quad (46)$$

The above equation can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}_B = c^2 / \mathbf{v} (1 - \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2 / c^2}) \quad (47)$$

In old frame S , due to $m_A = m_B$, the center point of the mass system at point C . Comparing Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, we get the velocity of point C in new frame S is \mathbf{u}_A . Thus, the total momentum of the mass system in new frame S is $(m_A + m_B)\mathbf{u}_A$, i.e. $(m_A + m_B)\mathbf{u}_B$, due to $\mathbf{u}_A = \mathbf{u}_B$. On the other hand, since point A is stationary, $m_B \mathbf{v}$ also represents the total momentum of the mass system. As per Eq.(46), we obtain

$$(m_A + m_B)\mathbf{u}_B = m_B \mathbf{v} = 2m_B \mathbf{u}_B / (1 + \mathbf{u}_B^2 / c^2)$$

Fig. 8

$\mathbf{u}_A = \mathbf{u}_B$ from Fig. 8
($m_A + m_B$) $\mathbf{u}_A = m_B \mathbf{v}$

Fig. 9

The above equation can be written as:

$$m_B = m_A(c^2 + \mathbf{u}_B^2)/(c^2 - \mathbf{u}_B^2) \quad (48)$$

Substituting Eq. (47) into Eq. (48) and noticing $c^2 - \mathbf{v}^2 = \sqrt{c^2 - \mathbf{v}^2} \times \sqrt{c^2 - \mathbf{v}^2}$, $1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2} = c/\sqrt{c^2 - \mathbf{v}^2}$, we obtain:

$$m_B = m_A/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}$$

\mathbf{v} is the velocity of particle B . m_A is a particle mass when it is at rest. m_B is the particle mass when it is in motion. To avoid confusing, we use symbols \mathbf{u} , m_0 , m to replace \mathbf{v} , m_A , m_B .

The relationship of mass and velocity:

$$m = \gamma(\mathbf{u})m_0 \quad (49)$$

Where $\gamma(\mathbf{u}) = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2} > 1$, $\mathbf{u} < c$

m_0 — represents the mass of a particle when it is at rest in a reference frame.

m — represents the mass of a particle when it is in motion in a reference frame.

m is a scalar, and it is related to speed, regardless of the direction of velocity.

\mathbf{u} — represents the velocity of a particle in a reference frame, or the relative velocity between a particle and a space point.

$\gamma(\mathbf{u})$ — represents the motion factor.

If the particle moves along x -axis direction, the Eq.(49) becomes:

$$m = \gamma(u)m_0 \quad \text{The direction of } u \text{ is along } x\text{-axis} \quad (50)$$

9.2 The relationship of mass and energy, and the definition of the kinetic energy

Here, we refer to "Wikipedia"[6] to derive the relationship of mass and energy. Physics defines $A = E_k$. A represents the work done by an external force exerted on a particle along a path; E_k represents kinetic energy of the particle. The kinetic energy of a particle is related to the particle velocity, and the particle velocity is related to a reference frame, so kinetic energy is related to a reference frame.

Let's divide particle energy into two parts: E_0 represents static energy when a particle is at rest in a reference frame, and E represents total energy when a particle is in motion in a reference frame. $\Delta E = E_k$ represents kinetic energy, i.e. a particle energy increment, $\Delta E = E - E_0$. p represents momentum of a particle, $p = m u$.

If an external force F exerted on a particle, and the particle has moved from point A to point B , and the velocity of the particle is increased from $u = 0$ to $u = u$, the work done by the F , i.e. the energy increment is:

$$\Delta E = \int_A^B \mathbf{F} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{AB} = \int_A^B \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{AB} = \int_A^B \frac{dp}{dt} d\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{AB} = \int_A^B \frac{d\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{AB}}{dt} dp = \int_0^u u d(mu)$$

Using partial integration, and as per Eq.(50), thus

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E &= \int_0^u u d(mu) = umu - \int_0^u umdu = \gamma m_0 u^2 - \frac{m_0}{2} \int_0^u \gamma d(u^2) \\ &= \gamma m_0 u^2 + \frac{m_0 c^2}{2} [2(1 - u^2/c^2)^{1/2} - 2] \end{aligned}$$

After finishing, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E &= \gamma m_0 c^2 - m_0 c^2 \\ &= mc^2 - m_0 c^2 \\ &= E - E_0 \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Therefore, we obtain

The relationship of mass and energy:

$$E = mc^2 \quad (52)$$

This is the famous formula created by Einstein.

The Eq.(51) can be written as:

$$\Delta E = \Delta mc^2 \quad (53)$$

Eq.(53) is the another form of the relationship of mass and energy. It indicates that a small amount of mass change occurring on an object is equal to a great amount of energy released or received by the object.

From the Eq.(51), we get $\Delta E = (m - m_0)c^2 = (\gamma - 1)m_0c^2$. ΔE represents the kinetic energy E_k .

The definition of the kinetic energy:

$$E_k = (\gamma - 1)m_0c^2 \quad (54)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2} > 1, \mathbf{u} < c$$

The definition of kinetic energy in Newtonian mechanics is:

$$E_{k2} = \frac{1}{2}m_0u^2 \quad (55)$$

$E_k > E_{k2}$. It indicates that an object requires more external force or longer time to accelerate the object from $\mathbf{u} = 0$ to $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}$. Eq.(54) shows when $\mathbf{u} \rightarrow c$, $E_k \rightarrow \infty$. It verifies that the postulate of maximum speed is correct. Newtonian mechanics, Eq.(55), can be written as $u = \sqrt{2E_{k2}/m_0}$. It means the speed of an object can be unlimited as long as m_0 is smaller enough. When $u = 0.999c$,

$E_k = 43E_{k2}$. The Eq.(54) is a modification to kinetic energy of Newtonian mechanics.

9.3 The relationship of force and acceleration

Newton's second law can be written as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d\mathbf{p}}{dt} = \frac{d(m\mathbf{u})}{dt} = m \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{dt} + \mathbf{u} \frac{dm}{dt} = \gamma m_0 \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{u} \frac{d(\gamma m_0)}{dt}$$

Since $\frac{d\gamma}{dt} = d(1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2})/dt = \gamma \mathbf{u} \mathbf{a} / c^2 \times 1/(1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2)$, after finishing, we obtain

$$\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}/(1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2) \quad (56)$$

$$\text{or } \mathbf{F} = \gamma^3 m_0 \mathbf{a} \quad (57)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_x = \gamma^3 m_0 \mathbf{a}_x \quad \mathbf{F}_y = \gamma^3 m_0 \mathbf{a}_y \quad \mathbf{F}_z = \gamma^3 m_0 \mathbf{a}_z$$

$$\mathbf{F} = F_x \mathbf{i} + F_y \mathbf{j} + F_z \mathbf{k} \quad \mathbf{a} = a_x \mathbf{i} + a_y \mathbf{j} + a_z \mathbf{k}$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2}$$

Eq.(56) is a modification to $\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}$, and it indicates that external force required for accelerating an object is not only related to the object mass but also related the object velocity. When $\mathbf{u} \rightarrow c$, the $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, any object velocity cannot reach the speed of light. Eq.(57) can be written as

$\mathbf{a} = (\mathbf{F}/m_0) (1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2)^{3/2}$. When $\mathbf{u} \rightarrow c$, the $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow 0$. It means if a particle is subjected to an external force for long time, the particle will tend to a constant speed, which is close to the speed of light.

9.4 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of mass

As per Eq.(49), $m = \gamma m_0$, $m' = \gamma' m_0$, $\gamma' = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}'^2/c^2}$. For convenience, we derive a math equation as follows.

$$1/\gamma' = \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}'^2/c^2} = \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2} \times \sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2} \times 1/(1 - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2)$$

$$\text{i.e. } \gamma' = \gamma \gamma_v \beta \quad (58)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2}, \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}, \beta = 1 - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2$$

Substituting γ' into $m' = (\gamma'/\gamma)m$, we obtain

$$m' = \gamma_v \beta m \quad (59)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}, \beta = 1 - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2$$

If \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{u} directions are opposite, $\beta = 1 + \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2$

9.5 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of momentum vector

In frame S, momentum definition is $\mathbf{p} = m\mathbf{u}$. The components of momentum on three axes can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_x &= m u_x & p_y &= m u_y & p_z &= m u_z & m &= \gamma m_0 & \gamma &= 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}^2/c^2} \\ \mathbf{p} &= p_x \mathbf{i} + p_y \mathbf{j} + p_z \mathbf{k} & \mathbf{u} &= u_x \mathbf{i} + u_y \mathbf{j} + u_z \mathbf{k} \end{aligned}$$

In frame S', momentum definition is $\mathbf{p}' = m'\mathbf{u}'$. The components of momentum on three axes can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} p'_x &= m' u'_x & p'_y &= m' u'_y & p'_z &= m' u'_z & m' &= \gamma' m_0 & \gamma' &= 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{u}'^2/c^2} \\ \mathbf{p}' &= p'_x \mathbf{i} + p'_y \mathbf{j} + p'_z \mathbf{k} & \mathbf{u}' &= u'_x \mathbf{i} + u'_y \mathbf{j} + u'_z \mathbf{k} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting Eq.(27), (58) into $\mathbf{p}' = \gamma' m_0 \mathbf{u}' = (\mathbf{p}\gamma' \mathbf{u}')/(\gamma \mathbf{u})$, we obtain following equation for transforming momentum \mathbf{p} from frame S to frame S':

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}' &= \mathbf{p} \gamma_v (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) / \mathbf{u} & (60) \\ p'_x &= p_x \gamma_v (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) / \mathbf{u} & p'_y &= p_y \gamma_v (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) / \mathbf{u} & p'_z &= p_z \gamma_v (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) / \mathbf{u} \\ \text{Where } \gamma_v &= 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2} \end{aligned}$$

9.6 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of acceleration vector

In frame S, acceleration definition is $\mathbf{a} = d\mathbf{u}/dt$, and $\mathbf{a} = a_x \mathbf{i} + a_y \mathbf{j} + a_z \mathbf{k}$. In frame S', acceleration definition is $\mathbf{a}' = d\mathbf{u}'/dt'$, and $\mathbf{a}' = a'_x \mathbf{i} + a'_y \mathbf{j} + a'_z \mathbf{k}$. The \mathbf{u}' , t' and \mathbf{a}' are physical quantity in frame S'.

For deriving acceleration transformation from fame S to fame S', we must use math quantities. Math time is t'^* , and math velocity is $\mathbf{u}'^* = \mathbf{u}'$ since Eq.(27) is correct. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}' &= d\mathbf{u}'/dt'^* = (d\mathbf{u}'/dt)/(dt'^*/dt) \\ t'^* &= t - \mathbf{v}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{AC}/c^2 & (26) \\ \mathbf{u}' &= (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v})/(1 - \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}/c^2) & (27) \end{aligned}$$

Due to $d\mathbf{v}/dt = 0$ (\mathbf{v} is a constant velocity), we get $dt'^*/dt = 1 - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2 = \beta$ and $d\mathbf{u}'/dt = \mathbf{a}/(\gamma_v^2 \beta^3)$. Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}' &= \mathbf{a}/(\gamma_v^2 \beta^3) & \mathbf{a}' \neq \mathbf{a} & (61) \\ a'_x &= a_x/(\gamma_v^2 \beta^3) & a'_y &= a_y/(\gamma_v^2 \beta^3) & a'_z &= a_z/(\gamma_v^2 \beta^3) \\ \mathbf{a}' &= a'_x \mathbf{i} + a'_y \mathbf{j} + a'_z \mathbf{k} & \mathbf{a} &= a_x \mathbf{i} + a_y \mathbf{j} + a_z \mathbf{k} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2} \quad \beta = 1 - \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}/c^2$$

\mathbf{a}' in Eq. (61) is mathematical acceleration but it is equal to physical acceleration in frame S'. Again, math time t'^* is not equal to physical time t' . The definition of \mathbf{a}' is $\mathbf{a}' = d\mathbf{u}'/dt'$.

As per the Galilean transformation, the accelerations in frames S' and S are the same. Eq.(61) indicates that the acceleration of a particle is not independent of a reference frame. If the moving directions of a particle and frame S' are the same, it will be $\mathbf{a}' > \mathbf{a}$; if opposite, it will be $\mathbf{a}' < \mathbf{a}$. The logical acceleration transformation is not the same as relativistic mechanics.

9.7 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of energy

As per Eq.(52), $E = mc^2 = \gamma m_0 c^2$, $E' = m' c^2 = \gamma' m_0 c^2$. Substituting Eq. (58) into $E' = \gamma' E/\gamma$, we obtain

$$E' = \gamma_v \beta E \quad (62)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}, \quad \beta = 1 - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}/c^2$$

Noticing Eq.(62) and (59) are at the same form. This indicates an intrinsic relationship between mass and energy. The mass or energy is not invariant. It is related to the velocity of object, i.e. it is related to a reference system. Newtonian mechanics assumes mass is invariant, which makes Newtonian mechanics is not suitable for high-energy physics.

9.8 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of momentum-energy

The Eq. (60) can be written as $\mathbf{p}' = \gamma_v(\mathbf{u}\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{v}\mathbf{p})/\mathbf{u}$. Combining this equation with $\mathbf{p} = m\mathbf{u}$ and $m = E/c^2$, we obtain

$$\mathbf{p}' = \gamma_v(\mathbf{p} - E\mathbf{v}/c^2) \quad (63)$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}$$

9.9 The three-dimensional Logical transformation of force vector

From Eq.(57), $\mathbf{F} = \gamma^3 m_0 \mathbf{a}$, $\mathbf{F}' = \gamma'^3 m_0 \mathbf{a}'$, we get $\mathbf{F}' = \gamma'^3 \mathbf{a}' \mathbf{F} / \gamma^3 \mathbf{a}$. Substituting Eq. (58), (61) into this equation, we obtain

$$\mathbf{F}' = \gamma_v \mathbf{F} \quad \mathbf{F}' \neq \mathbf{F} \quad (64)$$

$$\mathbf{F}'_x = \gamma_v \mathbf{F}_x \quad \mathbf{F}'_y = \gamma_v \mathbf{F}_y \quad \mathbf{F}'_z = \gamma_v \mathbf{F}_z$$

$$\mathbf{F} = F_x \mathbf{i} + F_y \mathbf{j} + F_z \mathbf{k} \quad \mathbf{F}' = F'_x \mathbf{i} + F'_y \mathbf{j} + F'_z \mathbf{k}$$

$$\text{Where } \gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - \mathbf{v}^2/c^2}$$

Due to $\mathbf{a}' \neq \mathbf{a}$, the force \mathbf{F}' is not equal to \mathbf{F} . The Eq.(64) indicates that force is not invariant, and it is related to a reference frame. However, it is $\mathbf{F}' = \mathbf{F}$ in Relativistic mechanics. Since $\mathbf{a}' \neq \mathbf{a}$, why $\mathbf{F}' = \mathbf{F}$? It is in question.

9.10 The three-dimensional inverse Logical transformations of physical quantity

$$\text{The inverse mass transformation: } m = \gamma_v \beta' m' \quad \beta' = 1 + \mathbf{u}'\mathbf{v}/c^2 \quad (65)$$

$$\text{The inverse momentum transformations: } \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}' \gamma_v (\mathbf{u}' + \mathbf{v})/\mathbf{u}' \quad (66)$$

$$\text{The inverse transformation of acceleration: } \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}' / (\gamma_v^2 \beta'^3) \quad \beta' = 1 + \mathbf{u}'\mathbf{v}/c^2 \quad (67)$$

$$\text{The inverse energy transformation: } E = \gamma_v (1 + \mathbf{v}\mathbf{u}'/c^2) E' \quad (68)$$

$$\text{The inverse transformations of momentum-energy: } \mathbf{p} = \gamma_v (\mathbf{p}' + E'\mathbf{v}/c^2) \quad (70)$$

$$\text{The inverse transformation of force: } \mathbf{F} = \gamma_v \mathbf{F}' \quad (71)$$

$$\text{If } \mathbf{v} \text{ and } \mathbf{u} \text{ directions are the same, } \beta' = 1 - \mathbf{u}'\mathbf{v}/c^2$$

From above a series of equations, they indicate that mass, energy, force are measurable physical quantities. They are all related to a frame of reference. The inverse transformations are equivalent to a particle moving in opposite direction of \mathbf{v} . Eq.(71) and Eq.(64) are the same form. It indicates Newton's third law $\mathbf{F} = -\mathbf{F}'$ is valid.

10. Conclusion

The physical time of frame S' and frame S are the same, since both frame S' and frame S use the same standard clock (defined by physics, located at Greenwich, London) to measure time, and since all physical laws are the same in frames S and S' . The standard clock is a measurement tool, and a moving observer cannot make it goes slower or a moving standard clock does not go slower.

If we know a particle velocity in frame S , the particle velocity in frame S' can be calculated by a mathematical equation called velocity transformation. As everyone knows, velocity is a function of time. In order to get the **correct result**, we must use the **mathematical time** of the frame S' instead of the physical time. The relationship between the mathematical time (t'^*) of frame S' and physical time (t) of

frame S is determined by a time transformation equation. Since $t^* < t$, we say that a moving "clock" goes slower. If u and v directions are opposite, it will be $t^* > t$ as per Eq.(29). When observer S sees math clock of S' goes slow, the observer S' will see math clock of S goes faster. When observer S sees observer S' is moving, observer S' sees observer S is also moving. This is logical, and this is true meaning of relativity.

The Lorentz speed transformation given by Einstein is correct. From the speed transformation, Einstein derived the famous mass-speed equation and mass-energy equation. However, the Lorentz factor in Lorentz transformation is superfluous, and it was eliminated when deriving the Lorentz speed transformation. The Lorentz transformation without the Lorentz factor becomes one-dimensional logical transformation. That is why the one-dimensional logical transformation of velocity is exactly the same as the Lorentz speed transformation. Since Lorentz transformation is derived based on Fig. 1, the x' -axis and x -axis overlap each other, and the moving direction of particle is along x -axis positive direction, Lorentz transformation is not applicable for particles moves in three-dimensional space. That is why the three-dimensional Lorentz transformations of physical quantities are contradictory and problematic.

In this paper, we derived three-dimensional logical transformation according to the principle of invariance of light speed, and three-dimensional setup of two reference frames. The logical transformation is for replacing Lorentz transformation and Galilean transformation. According to the logical transformation and the principle of invariance of relative velocity, we also derived three-dimensional formulas for the relationships of physical quantities, and a series of transformation equations of physical quantities. We believe these formulas and equations will be useful for high-energy physics, quantum mechanics, and clock correction of GPS. These formulas may be also useful for astrophysics, supersonic rocket, self-driving car.

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History Record:

- 1) This paper is the main part of a long paper. Original paper is divided into three papers.
- 2) Original paper is called "New theory of correcting Relativistic mechanics, Newton's second law and Newtonian mechanics". It was submitted to Nature Communication on 30th July 2019. Manuscript #NCOMMS-19-25599. File name: 218588_0_art_file_3974642_pvfyh1.pdf.
- 3) Original paper was also submitted to Foundations of Physics. The title is "A new theory for modifying relativistic mechanics and relativistic quantum mechanics". First time submission is on 08th Aug. 2019, submission ID: FOOP-D-19-00436, File name: FOOP-D-19-00436. Second time submission is on 13th Sep. 2019, submission ID: FOOP-D-19-00488. File name: FOOP-S-19-00542.pdf.